

Deconstructing Culture: An Interdisciplinary Critique of Contending Theories of Culture

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Adults engaged in the teaching about and researching society use the concept of “culture” as a valuable tool of analysis. However, a problem arises. While “culture” is an often-used term, it is rarely defined. The goal of this inquiry was to provide a comprehensive discussion of the concept of culture from different disciplines. Far from having a singular definition, culture is a contested category. While well-known and often cited, Hofstede’s cultural analysis is problematic, as it provides a useful but insufficient, binary, and immutable framework. Within this paper we examine culture from different perspectives and disciplines, such as anthropology, business, history, philosophy, political economy, and sociology. Anthropology views culture as all-encompassing; business and management, dichotomous and inert; history, ever-changing; philosophy, immutable or dialectical, as well as idealist or materialist; political economy, interacting with the economy and politics; and, sociology, as interacting, conforming, or opposed to the social order. Adult education incorporates these definitions depending on the context. In general, this paper provides a smorgasbord of contending explanations from which adult educators, adult learners, human resource practitioners, and academicians can choose their framework in analyzing and working with individuals and groups in society.

Introduction

“Culture” is an important consideration when working in community, adult, and higher education, yet culture is a difficult concept to generalize or confine through theoretical or practical understandings. For example, the popular understanding of culture problematically equates culture with other descriptors of diversity and ways to categorize people, such as sex, age, color, and ethnicity.

A critical review of academic literature reveals that culture is often treated as (1) immutable and (2) structurally binary, both of which provide insufficient explanations of actually existing social phenomena and relations. Using a post-structuralist deconstructionist stance (Derrida, 1978), this survey of literature reveals that culture is not confined to two ends of a spectrum, but measured along multiple spectrums and with much complexity.

This paper answers the following questions:

1. What is the critique of Hofstede’s model, which is the dominant view of culture in community, adult, and higher education?
2. What are the alternative discourses from different disciplines from which a richer understanding of culture can be attained?
3. What are the implications of the deeper understanding of culture on the future direction and practice of adult educators and adult learners?

Methodology

Most literature in adult education and human resource development, among others, presents a one-dimensional perspective of culture. This interdisciplinary, critical review of literature poses contending views of culture and suggests multi-dimensional perspectives of culture. To complete the literature review, we dissected the elements of mainstream views of culture from the fields of education, business, management, communication and human resource development. This paper presents alternative perspectives from various disciplines, among which are philosophy, anthropology, history, political economy, and sociology in order to present richer and deeper appreciation of culture. As this paper is only focused on the various definitions of the word “culture” in the different fields, “culture” was the keyword used in a search for literature. While scouring and evaluating different literatures, only seminal works and the latest textbooks that contain the word “culture” were considered. Literature to which textbooks within and across the disciplines always make reference reveal that they are seminal works. Hard copies and electronic copies of reading materials were obtained. After searching for, reading, and analyzing the literature on “culture,” the key definitions of “culture” from the reading materials across the disciplines were extracted and recorded and categorized.

Findings

What Is Culture? In general, everything that is not nature is culture (Lévi-Strauss, 1961). Kant was the first person to use the term “kulture,” which meant “civilization”, while Gustav Klemm was the first to use the term “culture” in an anthropological sense (Omohundro, 2008, p. 35). The term culture properly belongs to cultural anthropology. Anthropologists break down all the elements of culture to include material products, ideas, values, norms, and symbols (Kornblum, 2008), such as language, literature, and philosophy. Culture is learned, symbolic, and shared; as culture is all-encompassing and integrated, “[w]hen one behavior pattern changes, others also change” (Kottak, 2009, p. 33). Tylor (1871, p. 1) provided the first definition of culture, according to which: “Culture, or civilization... taken in its wide ethnographic sense is that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society.” Culture refers to “the learned, socially acquired traditions of thought and behavior found in human societies. It is a socially acquired lifestyle that includes patterned, repetitive ways of thinking, feeling, and acting” (Harris & Johnson, 2007, p. 10). Ember, Ember, and Peregrine (2007) refer to culture as

the customary ways of thinking and behaving of a particular population of society. The culture of a social group includes many things—its language, religious beliefs, food preferences, music, work habits, gender roles, how they rear their children, how they construct their houses, and many other learned behaviors and ideas that have come to be widely shared or customary among the group. (p. 6)

Taken together, culture refers to (1) “a general process of intellectual, spiritual, and aesthetic development,” (2) “a particular way of life... of a people, a period or a group,” (3) “the works and practices of intellectual... and artistic activity” such as music, dance, theater, cinema, painting, and sculpture (Williams, 1976, p. 80). It also refers to “the signifying system through which... a social order is communicated, reproduced, experienced and explored” (Williams, 1981, p. 13).

What is the Dominant Discourse? Hofstede's binary model (2001) is the most cited literature used in adult education, business, management, leadership, human resources development and other related fields. The elements of Hofstede's cultural dimensions include power distance, individualism-collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, masculinity-femininity, long-term-short-term orientation, and gratification. Like Huntington's clash of civilization (1992), Hofstede's model is useful for synchronic cross-cultural comparison or which "describe[s] a culture at one period in time" (Peoples & Bailey, 2012, p. 96). The merit of the dominant view of culture is also its disadvantage. There are many problems with Hofstede's model. One, Hofstede's binary model over-generalizes, as though there are no similarities at all among societies. Anthropologists, however, point out that there are not only particular but also universal and general cultural traits (Kottak, 2009). Two, Hofstede's model generalizes culture from the national level of analysis only, which is quite partial. Culture must also be analyzed from the individual, group, class, societal, state, regional, international, global, and other levels of analysis. By only focusing on cultural particularism and cultural relativism, Hofstede non-dialectically falls victim to cultural ethnocentrism, missing out on the possibility of some degree of cultural universalism (Peoples & Bailey, 2012; Spradley & McCurdy, 2012). Three, more sophisticated models discuss the McDonaldization (Barber, 1992), hybridization, and "glocalization" of culture (Robertson, 1994), but all these only provide nothing but caricatures. Four, people go through not only a process of enculturation early in life but also acculturation to new ideas, values, and behaviors later in life (Miller, 2007). Five, Hofstede's model is not capable of capturing diachronic changes in culture. Hofstede's immutable and ahistorical model misses out on diachronic analysis that "studies the changes in culture of a people over time" (Peoples & Bailey, 2012, p. 96). The succeeding section provides more discussions about culture from the other fields.

What are the Alternative Discourses from the Different Disciplines? To the dominant discourse that promotes a non-viable dichotomous caricature of culture (Merriam, Caffarella & Baumgartner, 2007), we present alternative views from cultural anthropology, history, philosophy, political economy, sociology, and business. Different fields provide different factors and rationale that explain certain types of culture. Anthropologists study "[d]ifferences and similarities in contemporary and historically recent cultures; causes and consequences of socio-cultural change; impacts of globalization and contacts on the world's peoples" (Peoples & Bailey, 2012, p. 3). Anthropologists espouse contending views, such as functionalism, behaviorism, materialism, idealism, neo-evolutionism, holism, universalism, or cultural relativism. Cultural anthropologists focus "on human cultural behavior and cultural systems and the variation in cultural expression among human groups" (Park, 1999, p. 11). The ontologically materialist paradigm, for example, provides "economic, ecological and biological explanations" (p. 35), while the ontologically idealist paradigm provides "interpretive," "symbolic, representational" and "postmodern" explanations (Bates & Franklin, 1999, p. 35). The behaviorist view considers culture as composed of "learned and shared ways of behaving" (Miller, 2008, p. 31). The holistic view considers culture as consisting of "learned and shared beliefs, meanings, and symbols *as well as* learned and shared ways of behaving" (Miller, 2008, p. 31).

History as an academic discipline is the study of the genesis, evolution, and the stages of development of societies, of which there are some major trends, namely the maintenance of the status quo, reform, revolution, and the return to the old order. "Cultures are products of history" (Omohundro, 2008, p. 36). However, interpretations of historical events in turn are a product of

culture. Cultural anthropologists deal with “universals and variation in culture in the past and present” (Ember & Ember, 2007, p. 6). Note, however, that usually the conquerors write history, as a consequence of which, other people’s history becomes ignored, deprioritized, and “othered.” Power dictates how history is presented, what artifacts are valued, and what level of provenance is needed for a piece of information to be considered fact (Foucault, 1980).

Philosophy is the study of “the general nature of the world (metaphysics or theory of existence), the justification of belief (epistemology or theory of knowledge), and the conduct of life (ethics or theory of value)” (Honderich, 1995, p. 666). Philosophers refer to the dialectical and immutable views of culture. The study of reality is divided into materialist and idealist ontology. Cultural idealists, symbolists or interpretivists consider culture as consisting of “learned and shared beliefs, thoughts, meanings, and symbols” (Miller, 2008, p. 31). Geertz (1973, p. 89) wrote a seminal work, according to which culture refers to "a system of inherited conceptions expressed in symbolic forms by means of which men communicate, perpetuate, and develop their knowledge about and attitudes toward life." Disagreeing with the standard definition of culture, Geertz (1973, p. 44), in his seminal work, wrote:

Culture is best seen not as complexes of concrete behavior patterns—customs, usages, traditions, habit clusters—as has been the case up to now, but as a set of control mechanisms—plans, recipes, rules, instructions (what computer engineers call ‘programs’)—for governing of behavior.

Political economy is the study of the dynamic relationship between the economy, politics, and culture, investigating stagnation, change, clash, convergence, wealth, and poverty, through space (different social contexts) and time (different historical moments). Cultural materialists view society as composed of (1) infrastructure, including production and reproduction (2) structure, including domestic economy and political economy, and (3) superstructure, such as belief system, religion, ideology, art, and sports (Harris & Johnson, 2007). The economic base determines the political and cultural superstructure, which in turn influences the economy.

Sociology is “the scientific study of society and human behavior” (Henslin, 2012, p. G3). It is the study of human behavior, social interaction and social groups (Turner, 2006), conflict and convergence. It deals with groups and organizations, social interaction and structure, groups and organizations, crime, social class and stratification, global stratification and inequality, race and ethnicity, gender, sexuality, discrimination, families, religion, education, and health care, among others (Anderson & Taylor, 2013; Kimmel & Aronson, 2012; Schaefer, 2011). In sociology, culture is studied from the perspectives of all types of social behavior, including social interactions, social institutions, social organizations, social groups, social classes, social conformity, social conflict, and social change.

Conclusion

Summary. Culture defies having a singular definition. Anthropologists provide an integrated and all-encompassing definition, which includes, among others, things, ideas, beliefs, values, symbols, and behavior. Transmitted within a certain group from one generation to another, culture provides the tools to compare and contrast different societies through time. Historians explain that culture changes through time. Political economists portray the dynamic interaction among the economy, politics, and culture. Philosophers reveal that culture can be

viewed ontologically as unchanging or dialectically varies from one person or place to another. Sociologists explain the culture is used to maintain the status quo or to promote a change in the social order, which in turn affects the culture.

Through understanding this exploration of the literature, practitioners in community, adult, and higher education may better understand cultural differences and better serve adult learners with different cultures. Those who take Hofstede's binary classification of culture fall victim to maintaining a stagnant view of culture as well as stereotyping and universalizing certain traits of people as permanent. This paper presents alternative views of culture as complex, dynamic, and ever-changing. Educators will benefit from having a more profound view of culture, especially as they relate and are applied to adults in the community, work, and academic settings.

Implications of Application of the Findings to Practice. The greatest dangers of incomplete and incorrect understanding of culture in practice are stereotyping, bigotry, intolerance, ethnocentrism, and racism. By referring to us and them, we fall victim to the danger of othering (Derrida, 1978; Foucault, 1990; Lacan, 1966; Said, 1978). In opposition to the unsophisticated, crude, static, and binary view of culture, this paper argues that culture not only changes through time but is also free-flowing, socially determined, interpreted dynamically, and colored by experience. By providing alternative perspectives, the findings help adult educators and adult learners not only avoid such dangers, after which the greater respect for diversity can be promoted pro-actively.

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Presented at the Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education, University of Central Oklahoma, Edmond, OK, September 27–29, 2012.